

Bioprospecting and Biodiversity Commercialization in Nigeria: Strategic Pathways for Tropical Disease Drug Discovery

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ABSTRACT

Nigeria's extensive biodiversity and rich ethnomedicinal heritage present a critical opportunity to address global health challenges, particularly those related to tropical diseases such as malaria, leishmaniasis, schistosomiasis, and enteric fever. This paper explores the potential of bioprospecting and commercialization of indigenous bioresources as a pathway to drug discovery and economic development. Drawing on the Resource-Based View, National Innovation Systems, and the Entrepreneurial Ecosystem framework, the study examines the disconnect between Nigeria's ecological wealth and its marginal role in global pharmaceutical value chains. The paper identifies key barriers including weak legal frameworks, inadequate infrastructure, fragmented intellectual property regimes, and limited integration of traditional knowledge into formal research and development (R&D) as constraints to effective bioprospecting. It further highlights environmental degradation and ethical concerns such as biopiracy. Entrepreneurial opportunities are explored across sectors such as phytopharmaceuticals, nutraceuticals, botanical cosmetics, and bioremediation. Recommendations include strengthening research infrastructure, reforming policy to ensure benefit-sharing, investing in human capital, and promoting community-based enterprises. This interdisciplinary review offers a road map for utilizing Nigeria's biodiversity to promote inclusive innovation, enhance public health, and create a robust bioeconomy.

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INTRODUCTION

Nigeria, as Africa's most populous country and a globally recognized biodiversity hotspot, holds untapped potential to become a leader in biodiversity-driven drug discovery (Musa, 2023). Its varied ecological zones, from the Niger Delta mangrove swamps to the montane forests of the

Mambilla Plateau, harbor thousands of endemic plant and microbial species, many of which have longstanding medicinal applications in traditional health systems (Sofowora et al., 2013; Oates et al., 2016). These biological assets offer significant prospects for the development of bioactive

compounds to combat diseases such as malaria, leishmaniasis, schistosomiasis, and enteric fever, which continue to impose high morbidity and mortality burdens across sub-Saharan Africa (WHO, 2023).

Despite this rich natural endowment, Nigeria remains largely peripheral to global biopharmaceutical value chains. Countries like China and India have systematically integrated ethnopharmacology with modern drug development to create globally competitive phytopharmaceutical sectors (Ezekwesili-Ofilu and Okaka, 2019). In contrast, Nigeria's outputs in terms of patented plant-derived medicines and licensed active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs) remain negligible. This gap is not due to the absence of biodiversity or indigenous knowledge but stems from institutional and infrastructural constraints. These include inadequate laboratory infrastructure, fragmented research-to-market pipelines, weak intellectual property enforcement, and the absence of a nationally coordinated benefit-sharing mechanism (Ongu et al., 2023, Musa 2023).

A significant obstacle to innovation is the marginalization of traditional medicine in formal R&D systems. Although over 70% of Nigeria's population relies on herbal remedies for primary healthcare (Musa et al., 2011; Bamidele et al., 2011), such knowledge remains largely undocumented or unverified through scientific protocols. Consequently, the transition from ethnobotanical use to pharmaceutical formulation is virtually nonexistent. This situation also exposes Nigeria to biopiracy, where foreign firms extract and commercialize indigenous resources without compensating source communities (Wynberg and Chennells, 2009).

Nonetheless, emerging scientific and policy developments are beginning to alter this trajectory. Technological advances in metabolomics, genomics, and bioinformatics are enabling high-throughput screening of natural products, while the operationalization of the Nagoya Protocol in Nigeria provides a legal foundation for fair access and benefit-sharing (Federal Ministry of Environment, 2020). Meanwhile, the growth of innovation hubs and public–private partnerships, particularly in

Abuja, Minna, and Lagos, signals increasing momentum in biotechnology entrepreneurship (Umar et al., 2022).

This paper argues that Nigeria's biodiversity should be reconceptualized not merely as a cultural or ecological resource, but as a strategic innovation asset. Drawing on the Resource-Based View (RBV), National Innovation Systems, and Entrepreneurial Ecosystem frameworks, the study interrogates Nigeria's failure to convert biodiversity into scalable pharmaceutical outputs and proposes an integrative roadmap for bridging scientific discovery with commercial development.

THE BIODIVERSITY RESOURCE BASE

Biodiversity as a Strategic Asset for Health Innovation

Nigeria is endowed with extraordinary ecological diversity, spanning humid rainforests, Guinea and Sudan savannahs, montane ecosystems, arid Sahel zones, freshwater basins, and marine coastlines. This diversity sustains a rich assemblage of flora and fauna, many of which possess therapeutic potential and cultural significance (Olson et al., 2001; Oates et al., 2016). The ecological heterogeneity across zones such as the Cross River rainforest, Mambilla Plateau, and the Niger Delta underpins Nigeria's status as a mega-diverse nation in West Africa (IUCN, 2024).

Endemism and Therapeutic Potential

Several plant species found in Nigeria exhibit endemic traits and have been reported to contain bioactive secondary metabolites. For example, *Alchornea cordifolia* is traditionally used for managing respiratory and venereal infections, with phytochemical screenings confirming the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, and fatty acids like 9,12-octadecadienoic acid methyl ester (Enyiukwu et al., 2024). Similarly, Musa et al., (2011) reported *Anthocleista vogelii* Planch, *Morinda lucida*, *Triplochiton scleroxylon*, *Alchornea cordifolia*, *Cassia sieberiana*, *Mangifera indica*, *Anacardium occidentale*, *Nauclea latifolia*, *Daniela oliveri* and *Carica papaya*, are used for the treatment of various ailments including enteric fever, diarrhea, dysentery, malaria, common cold, convulsion, yellow fever, jaundice and dental caries.

Despite such promise, only a fraction of Nigeria's 7,895 documented plant species has been subjected to pharmacological validation (Sofowora et al., 2013). There is also a gap between ethnobotanical documentation and translational research required for biopharmaceutical development.

Traditional Knowledge Systems

Traditional medicine constitutes the primary healthcare modality for over 70% of Nigeria's population, particularly in rural areas (Bamidele et al., 2011). However, these practices are at risk of being lost due to oral transmission, absence of formal documentation, and erosion of indigenous languages. Integration of this knowledge into scientific research remains minimal, reflecting missed opportunities for bioprospecting and validation of local remedies (Ideh et al., 2019).

Efforts to bridge this gap have been attempted through national surveys and collaborations involving research institutes like the National Institute for Pharmaceutical Research and Development (NIPRD), which produced *Niprisan*, an anti-sickle cell phytopharmaceutical derived from indigenous plants (NIPRD, 2022). While this achievement offers a benchmark for biodiversity-driven drug development, replication across disease categories remains scarce.

Ecological Pressures and Conservation Needs

Nigeria's biodiversity is under severe pressure from deforestation, climate change, illegal wildlife trade, and urbanization. The country reportedly loses 3.5% of its forest cover annually, ranking among the highest deforestation rates globally (FAO, 2015). These ecological stressors not only reduce genetic diversity but also compromise the sustainability of plant species with potential medicinal value.

The proliferation of invasive species and unsustainable harvesting practices further endanger endemic flora, making conservation an urgent prerequisite for long-term bioprospecting (Simberloff et al., 2013; UNODC, 2020). Though protected areas and forest reserves exist, their enforcement and funding are often inadequate (Margules and Pressey, 2000).

Nigeria's biodiversity represents a critical but underutilized resource base for addressing endemic tropical diseases. The gap between ecological wealth and therapeutic innovation underscores the need for a coordinated national strategy that integrates conservation, traditional knowledge, and biopharmaceutical research.

BARRIERS TO BIOPROSPECTING

Despite Nigeria's immense biogenetic resources and rich ethnopharmacological heritage, the translation of biodiversity into pharmaceutical and commercial innovation remains severely constrained. These challenges are multifaceted, spanning legal, institutional, infrastructural, cultural, and ecological dimensions.

Legal and Regulatory Fragmentation

Nigeria's legal framework for bioprospecting is fragmented and underdeveloped. Although the country ratified the Nagoya Protocol in 2014 to ensure fair and equitable benefit-sharing from the use of genetic resources, the practical implementation of its provisions has been limited. The National Biosafety Management Agency (NBMA), established under the NBMA Act of 2015, provides regulatory oversight for biotechnology applications but does not adequately address traditional knowledge protection or access and benefit-sharing (NBMA, 2015). The lack of harmonized guidelines across ministries creates bureaucratic bottlenecks, deterring local and foreign investments in biodiversity-based R&D (Ohuruogun and Okoye-Asoh, 2014).

Moreover, many local communities—often the custodians of ethnobotanical knowledge—remain unaware of their rights under existing frameworks, and mechanisms for recognizing their intellectual contributions are either absent or weakly enforced (Chuma-Okoro and Oluwasemilore, 2022).

Weak Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) and Benefit-Sharing Mechanisms

The inadequacy of Nigeria's intellectual property (IP) infrastructure poses another major impediment. Traditional knowledge systems are rarely granted formal recognition, and existing IPR policies are poorly adapted to protect communal innovations (Adaji and Abdulrauf, 2024). This undermines both local incentives for

knowledge sharing and external interest in forming equitable partnerships.

Without codified benefit-sharing agreements and community protocols, Nigeria remains vulnerable to biopiracy, where foreign entities exploit native species and traditional formulations without compensating source communities (Laird and Wynberg, 2007). The absence of sui generis systems for the protection of genetic resources and traditional knowledge continues to fuel legal ambiguities and stakeholder mistrust.

Infrastructural and Research Deficits

Scientific infrastructure in Nigeria is grossly inadequate for high-quality bioprospecting. Most tertiary and research institutions lack the advanced laboratory facilities necessary for phytochemical screening, compound isolation, and toxicity studies (Ongu et al., 2023). Funding constraints further limit the ability to attract and retain skilled personnel in ethnopharmacology, pharmacognosy, and related disciplines.

Unreliable electricity, poor logistics, and limited cold-chain systems complicate field sample collection, storage, and transport. These infrastructural deficiencies widen the gap between field discoveries and lab validation, impeding the establishment of product pipelines (Ojeih et al., 2024).

Socio-Cultural Challenges and Knowledge Erosion

Bioprospecting relies heavily on the transmission of indigenous knowledge, much of which is orally conveyed and at risk of extinction. Historical marginalization, language loss, and intergenerational discontinuities have weakened the continuity of traditional medical knowledge (Amoakoh-Coleman et al., 2023). Moreover, cultural mistrust of formal research institutions—fueled by prior exploitative encounters—has made many communities reluctant to share knowledge, especially without guarantees of ethical engagement or benefit-sharing (Ohuruogu and Okoye-Asoh, 2014).

Environmental Degradation and Loss of Biodiversity

Deforestation, land degradation, and climate change continue to threaten Nigeria's biodiversity. The destruction of natural habitats

reduces the availability of medicinal plant species and disrupts the ecological networks essential for bioprospecting (FAO, 2015; Ansah et al., 2022). Invasive species, overharvesting, and illegal logging further undermine the stability of genetic reservoirs.

The absence of comprehensive biodiversity inventories and digital databases impedes the systematic identification, cataloguing, and conservation of pharmacologically valuable species (Simberloff et al., 2013).

Ethical Governance and Biopiracy

The ethical dimensions of bioprospecting remain underdeveloped in Nigeria's scientific and legal discourse. Biopiracy—unauthorized exploitation of local resources—continues due to regulatory loopholes and weak enforcement (Ohuruogu and Okoye-Asoh, 2014). The absence of prior informed consent, mutually agreed terms, and community participation in most collection efforts raises serious ethical concerns and undermines trust between researchers and local custodians.

Addressing these systemic barriers requires a coordinated, multi-stakeholder approach that aligns policy reform, institutional capacity-building, legal enforcement, and community engagement. Without such integration, Nigeria risks continued marginalization in the global bioprospecting and bioeconomy landscape.

ENTREPRENEURIAL OPPORTUNITIES IN BIOPROSPECTING: CATALYZING NIGERIA'S BIOECONOMY

Accessing Nigeria's biodiversity for commercial innovation provides a one-of-a-kind opportunity to promote inclusive growth, improve health outcomes, and spark a national bioeconomy. Entrepreneurship, supported by strong policy and scientific ecosystems, can transform raw biogenetic resources into value-added products across multiple sectors.

Phytopharmaceutical Development

The rising global demand for plant-based medicines presents a compelling opportunity for Nigerian startups and research institutions to collaborate on the development of standardized phytopharmaceuticals. By building on validated traditional knowledge and applying modern scientific methods—such as compound isolation,

standardization, and clinical testing—entrepreneurs can create products that meet both domestic and export regulatory standards (Iwu, 2014).

The success of *Niprisan*, developed by the National Institute for Pharmaceutical Research and Development (NIPRD) from local plant extracts for the treatment of sickle cell disorder, demonstrates the feasibility of such ventures (NIPRD, 2022). However, scaling these models requires dedicated investment in product development pipelines, regulatory support, and market access infrastructure.

Nutraceuticals and Functional Foods

Beyond pharmaceutical applications, indigenous plant species offer significant potential in the nutraceutical and functional food markets. Species traditionally used to manage metabolic and infectious diseases can be repurposed into dietary supplements, teas, and fortified food products. This segment offers relatively low barriers to entry and growing consumer demand both locally and internationally, particularly for products promoting immune health and chronic disease prevention (Ndhlovu et al., 2021).

Botanical Cosmetics and Personal Care

Nigeria's flora also offers high-value potential in the cosmetics and personal care industry. Botanical ingredients such as shea butter, baobab oil, moringa, and aloe vera are widely sought for their therapeutic, anti-aging, and moisturizing properties. Traditional skin and hair care formulas can be used by entrepreneurs to produce premium products with indigenous identity branding. This niche allows for natural product innovation while integrating sustainability and cultural heritage (Umar et al., 2022).

Agricultural Biotechnology and Biocontrol Agents

Bioprospecting can contribute to Nigeria's food security and sustainable agriculture through the development of eco-friendly biopesticides, biofertilizers, and crop enhancement formulations. Local entrepreneurs can capitalize on microbial and plant-based compounds to improve soil health and pest resistance, reducing the dependence on synthetic chemicals and improving smallholder yields (Chuma-Okoro and Oluwasemilore, 2022).

Environmental Bioremediation

Several native plants and microorganisms have phytoremediation and biodegradation capabilities that can be used to clean up oil spills, industrial waste, and heavy metals from contaminated environments. Entrepreneurs in this domain can deliver contract-based services to industries and municipalities while contributing to environmental sustainability goals (Ansah et al., 2022).

Intellectual Property and Licensing Models

As product innovation progresses, entrepreneurs must strategically manage intellectual assets. Patentable plant-based formulations, proprietary extraction processes, and trademarks represent monetizable IP that can be licensed to larger manufacturers or global distributors. Building institutional capacity for intellectual property registration and technology transfer offices is crucial for enabling knowledge valorization (King et al., 1995; Adaji and Abdulrauf, 2024).

Digital Platforms and Knowledge Exchange

The digital economy offers transformative tools for connecting stakeholders across the bioprospecting value chain. Platforms that enable virtual herbariums, marketplace exchanges, quality assurance tools, and traceability systems can bridge researchers, producers, and buyers. These digital tools not only improve market access but also support transparency and compliance with benefit-sharing obligations (UNCTAD, 2021).

Community-Based Enterprises

A critical pathway to inclusive bioeconomic development involves creating community-based enterprises that embed local populations in the value chain. From cultivation to processing and cooperative marketing, such models promote benefit-sharing and conservation awareness while sustaining traditional knowledge systems (Laird and Wynberg, 2007).

Education, Incubation, and Capacity-Building

Nigeria must invest in human capital to support the evolving bioeconomy. Entrepreneurial training programs focused on natural product development, IP management, biosafety regulations, and clinical validation are essential. The establishment of university-based

bioinnovation hubs, accelerators, and sector-specific incubators can create a robust pipeline of bioentrepreneurs (Ongu et al., 2023).

Regulatory Consultancy and Policy Advocacy

As the policy landscape evolves, demand for expert navigation through regulatory, biosafety, and intellectual property regimes will increase. Entrepreneurial ventures in regulatory consultancy, legal services, and policy advisory can bridge compliance gaps for startups and foreign partners entering Nigeria's biodiversity economy (Ojeih et al., 2024).

Nigeria's biodiversity can serve as a launchpad for a thriving bioeconomy. However, realizing its potential depends on aligning scientific discovery, entrepreneurial dynamism, and policy support. Strategic investments in incubation, regulation, and market linkages will be critical for opening this ecosystem and establishing Nigeria as a continental leader in biodiversity-based innovation.

Conclusion

Nigeria's biodiversity represents a significant but underutilized national asset with the potential to transform the country's public health and economic landscape through drug discovery and allied bioindustries. While indigenous knowledge systems offer a robust foundation for bioprospecting, systemic barriers, including regulatory fragmentation, inadequate infrastructure, weak intellectual property protections, and ethical governance gaps, continue to impede commercialization.

Addressing these challenges requires a coordinated approach that integrates scientific validation, regulatory reform, community engagement, and entrepreneurial innovation. The country must invest in translational research, institutional capacity, and policy frameworks that support equitable access and benefit-sharing, while protecting traditional knowledge holders.

Nigeria is well-positioned to use its abundant biodiversity to spearhead regional biopharmaceutical innovation initiatives, especially in the fight against neglected tropical diseases. In addition to improving health outcomes, realizing this potential will boost the bioeconomy, promote inclusive economic

growth, and improve Nigeria's position in the global governance of biodiversity.

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Conflict of Interest

None declared.

REFERENCES

- Adaji, A.E. and Abdulrauf, L.A., 2024. Intellectual property issues for open science practices in genomic-related health research and innovation in Africa. *Journal of Law and the Biosciences*, 11(2), p.1sae026. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jlb/1sae026>
- Amoakoh-Coleman, M., Vieira, D. and Abugri, J., 2023. Ethical considerations for biobanking and use of genomics data in Africa: A narrative review. *BMC Medical Ethics*, 24, p.108. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12910-023-00985-y>
- Ansah, C.E., Abu, I.-O., Kleemann, J., Mahmoud, M.I. and Thiel, M., 2022. Environmental contamination of a biodiversity hotspot—Action needed for nature conservation in the Niger Delta, Nigeria. *Sustainability*, 14(21), p.14256. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su142114256>
- Bamidele, J.O., Adebimpe, W.O. and Oladele, E.A., 2011. Knowledge, attitude and use of alternative medical therapy among urban residents of Osun State, Southwestern Nigeria. *African Journal of Traditional, Complementary and Alternative Medicines*, 8(3), pp.281–288.
- Change, I.P.O.C., 2001. Climate change 2007: Impacts, adaptation and vulnerability. *Geneva, Switzerland*.
- Chuma-Okoro, H. and Oluwasemilore, I.A., 2022. Intellectual property rights, agricultural biotechnology and food sufficiency: Strengthening the Nigerian intellectual property legal framework for food self-sufficiency in the aftermath of a global pandemic. *International Review of Law, Computers & Technology*, 36(1), pp.48–67. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13600869.2021.1997082>
- Enyiukwu, D.N., Amadioha, A.C. and Bassey, I.N., 2024. Ethnobotany and phytochemical composition of *Alchornea cordifolia* in Abia State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Traditional and Complementary Medicine Research*, 5(1), pp.6–18.

- Ezekwesili-Ofili, J.O. and Okaka, A.N.C., 2019. Herbal medicines in African traditional medicine. *Herbal Medicine*, <https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.80348>
- FAO, 2015. *Global Forest Resources Assessment 2015: How are the world's forests changing?* Rome: Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. <https://openknowledge.fao.org/server/api/core/bitstreams/29b8ae23-99f9-4a05-b796-9a35d02af29d/content>
- FAO, 2019. *The State of the World's Biodiversity for Food and Agriculture*. Rome: FAO.
- Federal Ministry of Environment, 2020. *Nigeria's Nagoya Protocol Implementation Framework*. Abuja: Federal Government of Nigeria.
- Ita, E.O., 1993. Inland fishery resources of Nigeria. *FAO Fisheries Technical Paper No. 129*. Rome: FAO. <https://www.fao.org/4/t1230e/t1230e00.htm>
- IUCN, 2024. *The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species*. Available at: <https://www.iucnredlist.org> [Accessed 15 October 2024].
- Ideh, J.E., Ogunkunle, A.T.J. and Jimoh, M.A., 2019. Botanical characterisation, drug indications and sustainability status of traditional oral powdered herbal formulations in Ogbomoso, Nigeria. *Journal of Medicinal Plants for Economic Development*, 3(1), p.a64.
- Change, I.P.O.C., 2001. *Climate change 2007: Impacts, adaptation and vulnerability*. Geneva, Suíça.
- Iwu, M.M., 2014. *African medicinal plants in the search for new drugs*. New York: Wiley.
- King, S.R., Carlson, T.J. and Moran, K., 1995. Biological diversity, indigenous knowledge, drug discovery and intellectual property rights: Creating reciprocity and preserving relationships. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 47(3), pp.83–93. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-8741\(95\)01349-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-8741(95)01349-0)
- Laird, S.A., and Wynberg, R. 2007. Access and Benefit-Sharing in practice: Trends in Partnerships Across Sectors, CBD Technical Series No. 38, 140 p
- Margules, C.R. and Pressey, R.L., 2000. Systematic conservation planning. *Nature*, 405(6783), pp.243–253. <https://doi.org/10.1038/35012251>
- Musa, D.A. 2023) *Exploring Nigeria's Natural Treasure Trove: A Pharmacological Biochemistry Journey from Plant to Pill*. 21st Inaugural Lecture of the Ibrahim Badamasi Babangida University, Lapai, Niger State, Nigeria.
- Musa, D.A., Nwodo, F.O. and Yusuf, G.O., 2011. A comparative study of the antibacterial activity of aqueous ethanol and chloroform extracts of some selected medicinal plants used in Igalaland of Nigeria. *Der Pharmacia Sinica*, 2 (1): 222-227
- National Biosafety Management Agency (NBMA), 2015. *National Biosafety Management Agency Act*. Abuja: Federal Government of Nigeria.
- NIPRD, 2022. *National Institute for Pharmaceutical Research and Development: Drug Development Portfolio*. Available at: <https://www.niprd.gov.ng> [Accessed 3 October 2024].
- Ndhlovu, P.T., Omotayo, A.O., Otang-Mbeng, W. and Aremu, A.O., 2021. Commercialization potential of six selected medicinal plants commonly used for childhood diseases in South Africa: A review. *Sustainability*, 14(1), p.177. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14010177> .
- Oates, J.F., Gippoliti, S. and Groves, C.P., 2016. *Gorilla gorilla ssp. diehli*. *The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species*, 2016. <https://dx.doi.org/10.2305/IUCN.UK.2016-1.RLTS.T9404A17963949.en>
- Ojeih, C.A., Ogidan, O., Oluwajobi, Y.F. and Adebayo, B.O., 2024. Biotechnology regulatory conundrum: Balancing innovation and oversight. *Journal of Sustainable Development Law and Policy*, 15(3), pp.124–138.
- Olson, D.M., Dinerstein, E., Wikramanayake, E.D., et al., 2001. Terrestrial ecoregions of the world: A new map of life on Earth. *BioScience*, 51(11), pp.933–938. <https://doi.org/10.1641/0006-3568>
- Ongu, I., Olayide, P., Alexandersson, E., Zawedde, B.M. and Eriksson, D., 2023. Biosafety regulatory frameworks in Kenya, Nigeria, Uganda and Sweden and their potential impact on

international R&D collaborations. *GM Crops & Food*, 14(1), pp.1–17.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/21645698.2023.2194221>

Simberloff, D., Martin, J.L., Genovesi, P., et al., 2013. Impacts of biological invasions: What's what and the way forward. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*, 28(1), pp.58–66.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2012.07.013>

Sofowora, A., Ogunbodede, E. and Onayade, A., 2013. The role and place of medicinal plants in the strategies for disease prevention. *African Journal of Traditional, Complementary and Alternative Medicines*, 10(5), pp.210–229.

Umar, A.M., Abdullahi, A., Abdulkadir, A. and Shinga, A.H., 2022. Nigeria as an emerging entrepreneurial ecosystem: Prospects and challenges. *The International Journal of Business & Management*, 10(3), pp.47–55.
<https://doi.org/10.24940/theijbm/2022/v10/i3/BM2203-010>

UNCTAD 2021. *Handbook on Special Economic Zones in Africa*. Geneva, Switzerland.
https://unctad.org/system/files/official-document/diaeia2021d3_en.pdf

UNODC, 2020. *World Wildlife Crime Report 2020: Trafficking in Protected Species*. Vienna: United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime.
<https://www.unodc.org/unodc/en/data-and-analysis/wildlife.html>

Wynberg, R. and Chennells, R. 2009. *Green Diamonds of the South: A Review of the SanHoodia Case*. In Wynberg, R., Chennells, R., and Schroeder, D. (eds) *Indigenous Peoples Consent and Benefit-sharing. Learning from the San-Hoodia Case*. Berlin: Springer.